

Quantum Free Particle Wavefunction Stationary in Variations of Momentum?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. June 11, 2024

In a previous note (1), we suggested that the free particle form $\exp(ipx)$ ensures momentum conservation through: $\int dx \exp(-ip_2 x) \exp(ip_1 x) = 0$ unless $p_1=p_2$ (one dimension). A similar form $\exp(iEt)$ or $\exp(-iEt)$ ensures conservation of free particle energy. In such a case, x and t are treated as independent variables, yet classically $x/t = v$ if $x=0$ when $t=0$. Here we ask: How is the classical velocity linked to the quantum free particle probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$?

We assume $P(p,E,x,t)$ is unknown and that one wishes to find a condition which links x and t to the classical velocity v which is contained in p and E . This suggests that in general x and t are not restricted by v , but p and E , being exact are.

From special relativity, $dE/dp = v$ for a free particle, so one may try taking $dP/dp = dP/dp$ partial + dP/dE partial v . A solution is then: $P(p,E,x,t) = \exp(-iEt+ipx)$ such that $dP/dp=0$ for the classical path. In other words, $P(p, E, x, t)$ is stationary in p to first order on the classical x, t path.

Probabilities Which Ensure Conservation of Momentum and Energy

In a two particle collision, momentum is conserved i.e.

Probability (p_3, p_4 final | p_1, p_2 initial) = 0 unless $p_1+p_2 = p_3+p_4$ (vectors) ((1))

In one dimension, the function $\exp(ipx)$ allows for ((1)) to be satisfied, but one has to introduce the variable x and integrate, i.e. one has an orthogonal function. This leads to the idea of a wavelength, \hbar/p , with p being precise, but x being uncertain and having different probability values $\exp(ipx)$.

Similarly, one may introduce a probability which conserves energy through $\exp(iEt)$ or $\exp(-iEt)$. In such a case, t is simply a variable needed to establish orthogonality through integration and there is no formal link of x and t to v . Classically, however, $v = dx/dt = x/t$ if $x=0$ when $t=0$.

Thus, if one starts with the notion of creating two probabilities which ensure momentum and energy conservation for a free particle, then one has a function $P(p,E,x,t)$ with p and E being precise and x and t being linked to the wavelength \hbar/p and time interval \hbar/E . In other words, x and t are associated with probabilities. How then does one link x and t to the classical v ?

Linking x, t to a Classical v

In order to link x, t to a classical v , we begin with a probability $P(p,E,x,t)$ with p and E being precise, but x and t not. We then seek a condition on P which yields a relationship between x and t which describes classical motion.

From special relativity $dE/dp=v$ from $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$ ((2)). This suggests that one take d/dp of P i.e.

$$dP/dp = dP/dp \text{ partial} + dP/dE \text{ partial} v \quad ((3))$$

If $dP/dp \text{ partial} = x$ and $dP/dE \text{ partial} = -t$ and $dP/dp=0$, then ((3)) yields

$$x/t = v \quad ((4))$$

Thus, $P = \exp(-iEt + ipx)$ for a non-indefinitely growing or shrinking probability.

In other words, instead of using conservation of momentum and energy through orthogonality, one may find a stationary condition applicable to $P(p, E, x, t)$ which yields a relation for x and t consistent to the classical velocity definition (for $x=0$ when $t=0$).

As a result, considering P stationary in p to first order yields classical motion. Traditionally, dE/dp is said to be associated with group velocity in a wavepacket, but we argue that the $dE/dp=v$, which follows directly from special relativity, may be used to find the form of a free particle probability, which allows x and t to vary outside the classical restriction, but yields the classical v restriction when $dP/dp=0$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, classical physics yields a constraint on x, t for a free particle. If one considers a probability which ensures conservation of momentum, then $\exp(ipx)$ is a solution, while $\exp(iEt)$ or $\exp(-iEt)$ ensures free particle energy conservation. Here x and t are variables which are not forced to comply with the $x/t=v$ for $x=0, t=0$ classical constraint.

We suggest that one may consider a general probability $P(p, E, x, t)$ with p and E precise and x, t not. We then ask: How does one find a condition on P which yields the classical x, t, v relationship? We suggest using dP/dp because from special relativity: $dE/dp = v$. This leads to $dP/dp \text{ partial} + dP/dE \text{ partial} v = 0$ so $dP/dp = x$ and $dP/dE \text{ partial} = -t$ yields a solution, i.e. $P = \exp(-iEt + ipx)$ for a non-indefinitely growing or shrinking p . We suggest that this is a different way to consider obtaining a probability linked to free particle motion, which allows for x and t values outside of the classical x, t, v restriction.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Conservation of Momentum in Terms of Probability, Space, Time (preprint, zenodo, 2024)